

IPBES TCA Chapter 2. Data Management Report 2.1 Literature review on visioning activities / IPBES Transformative Change Assessment

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Description: The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES Scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 2 should address Visions of a sustainable world – for nature and people. The chapter reports the process and outcome of visioning activities. It relies on the participation of various stakeholders.

Process overview

Protocol

Type of analysis/search/review: Expert knowledge and snowball search

Search languages: English

Method: References were retrieved through expert knowledge and snowball sampling searches. This process included:

- assessing references that are cited in publications that report the outcome of visioning activities
- consulting with practitioners who have conducted workshops that include vision development with the objective of better outcomes for nature and people.
- Consulting chapter 2 authors to get recommendations on further references that emerged from the elaboration of the visions' database.
- Consulting Sandra Waddock who has examined processes required for transformative change and recently published in this area (Catalyzing Transformation: Making System Change Happen 2023). Sandra recommended influential sources that emerged from her research.

Location and format of the data:

- **Initial list :**

3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.1- lit_rev_visioning_initital_articles

- **List of articles used in sections 2.2.1, 2.2.2 and 2.2.3 (A):**

4-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.1- lit_rev_articles_cited and used(A)

ID	Name	File type	Description
1	1-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.1- lit_rev_visioning_activities_V2	PDF	DMR
2	2-IPBES-TCA_chapter 2. DMR 2.1_lit_rev_visioning_activities_process2	JPG	Flowchart of the process
3	3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.1- lit_rev_visioning_initital_articles	PDF	Initial sample of articles
4	4-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.1- lit_rev_articles_cited and used(A)	PDF	Final list of articles